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MIMS 2.6.2 : Strategy & Dualism

The advantage that China seeks, which the Allies could have using the Law of Polarity, and some other metaphysical technologies as the foundation of our strategy; understanding strategy from a positional advantage perspective.

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ABSTRACT

The US Military has become excellent at tactics and Conventional warfare strategies. But their adaptability is either dubious, or hampered by political nonsense. China has nothing holding it back from utilizing a Total War doctrine which utilizes a Polar Complete Whole strategy involving the entire spectrum of warfare. After the failures in Iraq and Afghanistan, the NATO/Allies should take a step back, and look at the dualism created by rhetoric and agenda, and reassess a global strategy which is in keeping with the purpose of MIMS: to create a better world. War is the anti-MIMS, so upon this issue not only state survival, but mankind's survival does depend.

Keywords: MIMS - strategy - art of war - China - Pentagon - Shi 勢

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Figure 1 - The "big G" diagram; credit: author¹

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https://www.academia.edu/50300514/On_the_Membranous_Interface_of_the_Material_and_the_Spiritual_from_an_EPE

Review

In 2.6.1 the author covered the ancient MIMS of the concept of Shi.² Granted, the original metaphysical technology was devised for war, but it is postulated by F. Jullien³ and others to possibly extend to all sorts of strategic topics, including boardrooms⁴, courtrooms, sports, finance⁵, and more.

But as the author looks at the strategic philosophies of the East and West, and at human nature in general, there tends to form a sort of dualism. For example: Sun Tzu vs. Clausewitz/Alexander, or Conventional vs. Asymmetric, or us vs. them in general.

This is highly dangerous in an era of nuclear MADness, and other WMD. It is, also as the author is a medical professional, a matter of “healthy” or “infected,”⁶ and certain ideologies do represent a form of pathophysiology and often pathophysiological response. The response might be a spiritual matter and for discussion in an EPEMC::Religion paper separately.⁷ The pathology, etiology, and treatment of the response is covered already elsewhere⁸. What is not made clear, as of yet, is the nature of coeval survival, be it between estranged spouses, estranged voters, estranged political parties, or estranged countries.

In this the author will cover the typical thought, from Sunzi right through the Cold War, as well as look at how the “right” side can gain the advantage to bring about civil union. A special look at Lincoln’s Civil War and philosophy, as well as the results, may be necessary to elucidate clarity on the strategic matter from the MIMS perspective. It will be absolutely essential that the reader familiarize themselves with MIMS 2.7 & 2.8⁹, and it may be recommended that they cover “On the Origins of Religions,”¹⁰ beforehand as well. A cursory glance through early chapters of “The Art of Chess,”¹¹ by the author, and “Stone Monkey” by B. Holbrook¹² is highly recommended.

[MC perspective and Dual Double Layer Economics a proposed test of EPEMCs metallic properties tensile strength malleability durability](#)

² https://www.academia.edu/50357891/MIMS_and_Shi

³ “The Propensity of Things,” F. Julien, 1998

⁴ <https://english.ckgsb.edu.cn/knowledges/business-on-the-battlefield-sun-tzus-the-art-of-war/>

⁵ <https://www.financialsamurai.com/sun-tzus-art-of-war-applied-to-your-battle-against-debt/>

⁶ Health is not a duality but a spectrum.

⁷ It isn’t like capitalism and democracy are not known to create new sets of problems. They are improvements on the feudal/pillage/monarchy systems. But unfortunately, the economic setup requires some to be without. Sadly, the etiology tends to encourage youth to think “social problem” needs a solution of “socialism,” even when they don’t know precisely know what that means, or have any historical knowledge about the monstrosity of Marxist value systems (like Communism, Critical Theory, etc.) Hence the pathophysiological response is itself a pathology. Undealt with etiologies often result in these kinds of “compounded” cases in the Medicine. When we talk about “High Medicine” therefore we have to dig back into antiquity to look at issues. It may very well be that the West never cured the madness of democracy and Republics, or dealt with the inane nonsense of the “philosopher king.”

⁸ https://www.academia.edu/51022722/Winning_the_New_Cold_War_World_War_3

⁹

https://www.academia.edu/51641990/MIMS_2_7_8_War_and_Government_The_Rise_and_Fall_of_US_Military_Dominance_from_an_Art_of_War_perspective_and_MIMS_Analysis_as_well_as_a_short_discussion_of_the_history_of_failures_of_government_programs_from_antiquity_through_the_Great_Enlightenment

¹⁰ https://www.academia.edu/36753645/On_the_Origins_of_Religions

¹¹ https://www.academia.edu/40287817/Understanding_Chess_I_The_Art_of_Chess

¹² “The Stone Monkey : An Alternative, Chinese-Scientific, Reality,” B. Holbrook, 1981

Dualism... or Polarity?

Human psychology (and therefore spiritualism) tends towards an “us or them” mentality.¹³ Even God (in the Old Testament) appears this way, or at least this is how the Hebrews interpreted the particular peculiarities of the PPC¹⁴ and the planet god Elohim which was the source of the transcendent observations of the Force (*F* power) and of the greater consciousness called “The Lord” (*L* power) or the “tetragrammaton”¹⁵.

Why consciousness, at least in mankind, works this way is not the subject of this paper; here it is merely noted. What is important, though, is that we early on recognize that the Law of Polarity has several sub laws, of which the Chinese identified six, and the rest are found in the study of the Force (classical Electromagnetism, New Electromagnetism, etc.). Of these six main sub laws, duality belongs specifically to “mutual opposition.” This makes sense, because if we set it against Polarity, then we would have another Dualism and this would break the Law of Polarity. Instead, we see that dualism is unified within the Polar complete whole, as Bruce Holbrook called it. This polar complete whole (PCW) is the necessary component for the Principles (*P* power) to remain unified, substantiated, and true (hence yang in general). Let the reader understand therefore that the goal of this paper is to differentiate between the two epistemologies for the context of the polarities of strategy, and of strategy vs. tactics, not to say that one strategy set is opposed and better than the other strategy set. The Chinese identified these two sets in the past as Orthodox and Unorthodox. So while the west tries to “define asymmetric”¹⁶ the Chinese already defined it, without defining it (which is why there is still so much confusion).

Table 1 - The *P* power applied to MIMS 2.6¹⁷

<i>Heaven</i>	<i>Mind</i>	<i>Discussion</i>	<i>Modes</i>	<i>War</i>	
<i>Man/Mind</i>	Polarity	Strategy	Orthodox	Conventional	<i>Yang</i>
<i>Earth</i>	Duality	Tactics	Unorthodox	Asymmetric	<i>Yin</i>

Conventional vs. Asymmetric

Here the author notes that the West’s reactions to 9/11 and the Chinese text, “Unrestricted Warfare,”¹⁸ as well as to terrorism, insurgency, and guerilla warfare in the 1980s, is to basically treat “asymmetric” as “unfair.” This is a bit laughable since the US Military is literally the greatest in history, and its advantages over its enemies, save the Soviets, far exceeds any empires’ advantages over its competitors. The only thing unfair might be the asymmetric nature of “rules of engagement”¹⁹ which is what happens when bureaucrats are involved in making rules for soldiers.²⁰ But we digress. The main point is that the West tends to see the

¹³ <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/why-our-brains-see-the-world-as-us-versus-them/>

¹⁴ https://www.academia.edu/50912946/FAQ_EPEMC_MIMS pp. 6

¹⁵ YHVH, probably also the “peace sign” body of the four gas giants.

¹⁶ <https://apps.dtic.mil/sti/pdfs/ADA387381.pdf>

¹⁷ Please note the cross compliances with the 0 1 1 2 3 5 8 13

¹⁸ <https://www.c4i.org/unrestricted.pdf>

¹⁹ https://www.loc.gov/rr/frd/Military_Law/pdf/OLH_2015_Ch5.pdf

²⁰ “Lone Survivor,” M. Luttrell & P. Robinson, 2007

“straight up fair fight, knuckles bruised, face bloody” form of conventional war as “fair,” while loving the use of bigger, badder, techier weaponry than anyone else can afford. Furthermore, the advantage conferred by the Federal Reserve System²¹, an entirely ingenious (and possibly evil²²) MIMS of the late 1800s that came to be in the early 20th century and after WWII gave huge advantage to the Allied powers, seems to be ignored by the Military Industrial Complex (MIC) and her generals.

Regardless, the West might take heed of the adaptability of Sunzi and all the bingfa (for it has conventional warfare within it, and China is clearly increasing its spending in that direction knowing that in a street fight fancy kung fu moves mean nothing against raw, brutal, muscular pugilism²³ and dirty ground tactics²⁴); and America might itself take stock of the sobering lessons of Atlas, the lion, vs. the Bengali Tiger!²⁵

Orthodox vs. Unorthodox

The Chinese, by contrast, using their [EPEMC²⁶ confirmed-as-true] Chinese sciences²⁷ and being PCW, were able to more effectively look at the vertical scheme²⁸ and see that there is a MIMS behavior of Orthodox and Unorthodox.

- Because of the sub law “mutual penetration” and “infinite divisibility” there is the CvA in both Orthodox and Unorthodox. Thus the conventional Unorthodox is still Unorthodox, and so we see that the West’s dualism is: Orthodox Conventional vs. all Asymmetry and Unorthodoxy.
- Therefore the Asymmetric Orthodoxy gives the West a problem it should not, and would rather not have.²⁹
- The penchant for “true yang” of Conventional Orthodoxy notwithstanding, be it in American Football or boxing, the majority of the world does not share this ethic and cannot afford to.³⁰
- Therefore the proper course of action is for the Allies to develop a strategy MIMS that is adaptable.³¹

Strategy vs. Tactics

One thing the allies have done well is understand the concrete form of tactics vs. strategy, for many hundreds of years.³² However, culturally it is not necessarily clear. For the West a widespread confusion about this has remained despite the long years of chess tournament play, books, and high status enjoyed by

²¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/History_of_the_Federal_Reserve_System

²² “Creature from Jekyll Island,” G. Griffin, 1994 ; fiat violates the Laws of Thermodynamics.

²³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QrkkewDC54g>

²⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=u1OFABN1jic>

²⁵ Reading their fight reads like a textbook Art of War discussion on Orthodox or Conventional vs. Unorthodox fighting. https://military.wikia.org/wiki/Atlas_the_Barbary_lion_versus_the_Bengal_tiger_of_Simla

²⁶ https://www.academia.edu/36753648/Extended_Plasma_Electromagnetic_Cosmology_EPEMC

²⁷ https://www.academia.edu/37784032/Chinese_Natural_Philosophy_Physics_in_EPEMC

²⁸ To borrow the imagery of the *zongheng* school. Horizontal in this case would be as in Table 1.

²⁹ 9/11 would be an example. Presuming there were real airplanes that crashed kamikaze into the WTC towers, then this is a conventional but asymmetric act of war.

³⁰ Americans understood this when fighting the British... twice, and then saving the British... twice. It was lost after the Superpower USA ® gained too much advantage and self-confidence in the 1950s. The MIC ensured it. Ike did nothing to prevent it, only warn of it.

³¹ China has clearly devoted itself entirely to this, and has developed as robust a War Department of Military Studies, in the modern vein, as the Pentagon and its colleges. The Pentagon needs to understand this in its bones and adapt, and quit complaining. Leave the politics to the politicians and ambassadors!

³² Even thousands if one considers the wisdom of the Greeks at Thermopylae and the Roman conquests.

European and American, and of course Russian players. It does appear that Real Time Strategy (RTS) video games, Role Playing Games (MMO/RPG), and other means (like Fantasy sports trades, etc.) have elucidated this concept. But looking at American politics, where even the dirtiest players manage to mess up slam dunk strategies with poorly thought out tactics and cross-purpose stratagems, it is clear that segments of the populace do not understand. By contrast, we know too little about the Chinese and other New-Axis populations to make a good judgment, but in general they appear to avoid any and all such thinking as their “betters” would prefer, because otherwise they get destroyed by excessive tyranny, party purges, coups, and genocidal programs (various).

But in the higher echelons of the Communist militaries, it is clear that a good deal of time is put into understanding strategy and stratagems, and then having whimsical fantasies about tactically striking their neighbors and the “Great Satan” (or Hegemon): America. The author doesn’t see much proof that they have a very secure foundational understanding of tactical methods, while the West has moved so far into tactical strikes that there appears to be a crisis in Strategy!³³

Unification

When looking across these four columns and the “five domains” - Cyber, Land, Sea, Air, and Space - we see that there is a great need for unification. The benefits therewith will be discussed towards the end. The main facility of a MIMS is to bring the material (or real) need to the spiritual (psychological or PPPC) and have reception of it, be it divine or man’s consciousness, communing with the Universal Energy Source (Source, for short).

Therefore, the purpose of unification is to fulfill needs. And dear reader, there has never been a greater need than now, to solve this riddle and paradox before the problems multiply and worsen. In medical speak, the body of Mankind may already have cancer. Or we may be with pre-cancerous, but metastatic cells. In either case, no matter the progress we have made in material things, in the reduction of sin, in the reduction of prejudice, in the reduction of poverty... it is defied by the obviousness of the worsening state of certain situations and systems that hitherto have been relied upon, perhaps too much³⁴ or in isolation. We should rely on the PEMF or *F* power, but not at the expense of the planet, each other, social convention, common sense about catastrophe, and our relationship to the *L* power and God (the “Big G”)!

What we humans are doing to forests, oceans, arable land, children, and each other is inexcusable!

War, being the dangerous anti-MIMS, is key to be prevented. Sunzi said,

“1. Laying Plans

1. Sun Tzu said: The art of war is of vital importance to the State.

*2. It is a matter of life and death, **a road either to safety or to ruin.** Hence it is a subject of inquiry which can on no account be neglected.*

3. The art of war, then, is governed by five constant factors, to be taken into account in one’s deliberations, when seeking to determine the conditions obtaining in the field.

*4. These are: (1) **The Moral Law**; (2) Heaven; (3) Earth; (4) The Commander; (5) **Method and discipline.**”³⁵*

³³ See: Biden’s botched withdrawal from Afghanistan, and Obama’s accidental creation of the Islamic State.

³⁴ Think: oil, debt, and war diplomacy.

³⁵ Sunzi Bingfa, Chapter 1, transl. By L. Giles; <http://classics.mit.edu/Tzu/artwar.html>

What did he mean by “a road to safety or to ruin”? This is a Dao 道, or path, and therefore connects to the *F* power, PEMS, directly in both empirical observation and mythical historicity³⁶. But it also means “a way of”, and is also a verb - as in a perpetual action (of becoming). Ruin is a disastrous form of misfortune, and the reader might review MIMS 2.1.1 to understand the Aether or *A* power’s role in this a bit clearer.³⁷

As for the five constant factors, it is clear that Sunzi most valued the Moral Law. Interesting here he did not specify morality perse, or Confucianistic ethics³⁸, but appears to have made an inference to De 德. This paper is not about De or Moral Law, so suffice it to say it will be a good topic for a future MIMS discussion. However, let us confine ourselves to the concept of “the good”³⁹. We will, therefore, say that the MIMS of strategy, in a PCW, should be defined to “that which guides war or conflict towards the Moral Law, towards good.”

This will keep war from becoming an anti-MIMS, by *ending it as soon as possible*. Part of the evils of World War I - aside from the mustard gas and slaughter, of course - was the interminability of it. Air technology was not sufficient to defeat trench warfare, or to commit surgical strikes upon the Kaiser’s ridiculous and pompous military structure. And firearm and tank technology was just adequate enough to create true, destructive human misery. From all accounts and documentary footage⁴⁰, it was Hell on Earth.⁴¹

This is something which hearkens back to the 400 years of the Warring States⁴² period, and other similar periods in Europe’s histories.⁴³ When war lingers, it festers and rots a society. Whatever good that grows, withers, or is ruined⁴⁴. That is the state of conflict that enables two sides to be perpetually self-righteous, and strong enough to “hold their own.”

It is not clear that China knows this, but Americans and allies are learning this tough lesson withdrawing out of Afghanistan. But being weakened in “moral force” (Qi), by it, and by the economics of the situation and the optics of the reporting, has enabled a chance for China to “take advantage” of the allies’ confusion, turmoil, embarrassment, etc. to expand their arsenal, and position.⁴⁵ Luckily, India⁴⁶, Malaysia⁴⁷ and Japan⁴⁸ are waking up that NATO is not what it once was⁴⁹, and they are willing to provide a bit of bluster. However, if this were to turn to actual conflict, that would be incredibly unfortunate for all concerned! So it is because the NATO powers do not understand strategy, or the MIMS, or the Changes which govern Fate by mediating the Law of Causality with the Law of Evolutionary Flux, that the crisis is interred. Some will say “well it’s about time for a sequel to WWII” but that’s an incredibly pessimistic take on things given since WWII we have had civil rights and gender

³⁶ https://www.academia.edu/38590072/Shang_Di_Heaven_and_Dao

³⁷

https://www.academia.edu/50901241/MIMS_2_1_1_2_Aether_Business_and_Analytics_With_a_short_reflection_upon_the_philosophies_of_Ayn_Rand_and_the_concepts_of_Fortune_as_it_relates_to_the_Aether

³⁸ Humanism, Beneficence, Magnanimity, Virtue, etc.

<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s40636-016-0055-0>

³⁹ “To know the good is to do ‘the good’” ~Aristotle

⁴⁰ “They Shall Not Grow Old,” P. Jackson, 2019

⁴¹ See also: “1917” the movie

⁴² <https://www.britannica.com/event/Warring-States>

⁴³ Thirty Years War, Crusades, and the like.

⁴⁴ Think: Yugoslavia

⁴⁵ “Wait at leisure while the enemy labors,” China loves this one also for getting free R&D

https://military.wikia.org/wiki/Thirty_Six_Stratagems#Wait_at_leisure_while_the_enemy_labors

⁴⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2020%E2%80%932021_China%E2%80%93India_skirmishes

⁴⁷ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HIZ32_Ba11s

⁴⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=r2Pvhk4M4fl>

⁴⁹ Look at the military spending, at how the UK slipped from second place starting near 2012, Ibid. pp. 10, Figure 10

equality - indeed overparity⁵⁰. But, be that as it may, the Moral Law would stipulate that "that which guides war" be short acting, and long-preventing, as long as possible (until the MADness is cured). Christians don't believe it can be cured on Earth or by mankind.⁵¹ Yet we also know it cannot be cured by old religions worshipping planet gods which struck each other with cosmic thunderbolts, or with bad MIMS 2.7 (government) programs like ritual sacrifice.⁵² If that were the case, the elite would be able to do it *now*.⁵³

⁵⁰ All the studies show that girls are outperforming boys, except at sports, and that boys are not doing well at all. This is a tragedy. To make girls stronger you need not make boys weaker.

⁵¹ "Who's in Charge of a World that Suffers?" B. Graham, 2021

⁵² Psalm 51:16 "For Thou desirest not sacrifice, else would I give it; Thou delightest not in burnt offering."

⁵³ See: Bohemian Grove and the following wikileaks for a minutia of a plethora of evidence extant (if you look for it);

"From: Cheryl Mills **To: Hillary Clinton**

Date: 2009-08-28 13:30 Subject: HONDURAS: MAYBE, MAYBE

UNCLASSIFIED U.S. Department of State Case No. F-2014-20439 Doc No. C05764911 Date: 07/31/2015

RELEASE IN PART

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From: Mills, Cheryl D <MillsCD@state.gov>

Sent: Saturday, August 29, 2009 8:30PM

To: Subject: Fw: Honduras: Maybe, maybe

Fyi

From: Kelly, Craig A

To: Mills, Cheryl D; Abedin, Huma; Sullivan, Jacob 3

Cc: Smith, Daniel B; Macmanus, Joseph E

Sent: Sat Aug 29 16:53:56 2009

Subject: Fw: Honduras: Maybe, maybe

Attached is from Lew Amselem, our rep to OAS. He gives a readout of his conversation today with Arias Accord negotiator Jon Biehl. Some nice comments about S from Biehi and Arias. I will forward another note from Hugo Llorens with similar message. Best, ck

From: Amselem, W Lewis To: Task Force Honduras; Otero, Maria Sent: Sat Aug 29 13:54:22 2009

Subject: Honduras: Maybe, maybe

From: amselem

To: Amselem, W Lewis

Sent: Sat Aug 29 13:51:00 2009

Biehi called a little after 1:30 pm to say the meeting with the de facto envoys had been abruptly cancelled -- but for perhaps a positive reason.

Micheletti has asked about half the team to return to Tegucigalpa (Corrales stayed, as "he seeks to confirm that he will not lose his visa"). In the phone call he got from the de facto envoys as they headed for the airport,

Biehl said he detected a positive attitude. The envoys seemed confident they would get M to sign the SJ Accord. The envoys promised to call Biehl late this afternoon with the news from Honduras. If, if, if, if, the news is positive, Biehl and OAS Political Director Victor Rico will leave for Tegucigalpa tomorrow morning to meet Micheletti, make sure this is not another time-wasting tactic, and get something in writing from him that he agrees to the Accord and will sign it.

Just before speaking to me, Biehl had spoken with Arias who expressed cautious optimism that we might have a break-through. Arias told Biehl to tell us, that if that happens the United States gets the credit.

Arias said the US has played the game exactly right, with the appropriate mix of carrots, sticks, toughness, unified message, even-handedness and, above all, good timing. Arias said the Europeans have been calling him over the past two days, and have fallen into line with the US; the Swedes, as head of the EU, and have told him that they will take their cue from the US and will support US actions. Arias, Biehl said, was extremely complimentary of the "great political instincts shown by Secretary Clinton."

How to Unify

The first step to unification is simply seeing that there is a need, and then acting to remove dualistic expectations. Take, for example, that a US colonel went onto “Smarter Every Day” and threatened China implicitly.⁵⁴ This was either a) a blustering reactionary response to Chinese moves outwitting the Pentagon or b) a well calculated psychological attack that was *designed* to be Orthodox but asymmetric, which would make this an odd tactical strike (via social media).

The author would like to believe it was the latter, but common sense pushes him to believe the former. The colonel *looked like* he was making a blustering statement, and he looked *angry* about the topic, almost dismissive. This would, potentially, fall under the issue of the “arrogant generals” in Chinese bingfa texts like the Taigong, or the Zhuge Liang bingfa, etc. The reason they were to be distrusted is precisely because of the “full steam ahead” mentality many possessed, and their doggedness about matters of honor, loyalty, duty, and tendency to let anger control them in a firefight. That gets men killed, and then even the “good” side can lose. The Allies won the first two world wars not only because God was on their side, but because they kept their heads. If they cannot keep their heads this time, then the world truly could fall into a place of One World Government; a proverbial “boot stamping on your face, forever.”⁵⁵

So unifying strategy first comes down to recognizing one’s ignorance on the matter of dualism, and then correcting it by seeing the spectrum of fully polar complete wholeness.

For example, when it comes to conventional vs. asymmetric vulnerabilities, does the strategy involve creating a unified response, with a unified outcome? Or does it pre-suppose one side is best and so long as enough of the other side dies, then eventually it will learn to be submissive and become “good?” Because this latter describes the War on Terror, and also the arrogance of it and the failure of it. It describes a losing strategy, filled with lots of genius tactics, expensive campaigns⁵⁶, and strategies which only ever could lead to death⁵⁷, destruction, and failure⁵⁸.

In general the arrogance with which the US Military publishes even recent journals and reports, as a mental assault upon the “enemy” (mostly China and Russia) is a bit disturbing, as it violates the Cold War mentality of “I want to know what you don’t and you can’t know what I know.” This was a good policy, and just because the first Cold War ended does not mean it was no longer necessary.

For a researcher, the plethora of strategy texts and research dissertations, declassified documents, etc. is overwhelmingly positive. But it is also not wise to teach enemies everywhere what you think, how, and why. It is patently foolish. While Chinese is readily translated by the US military, the common People, Guard, and militias cannot read their texts. But much of their population can read our Internet. If and when US

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UNCLASSIFIED U.S. Department of State Case No. F-2014-20439 Doc No. C05764911 Date: 07/31/2015

With fingers crossed, the old rabbit’s foot out of the box in the attic, **I will be sacrificing a chicken in the backyard to Moloch . . .**

Tri” (sic) <https://wikileaks.org/clinton-emails/emailid/14333>

⁵⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qOTYgcdNrXE>

⁵⁵ George Orwell

⁵⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/International_military_intervention_against_ISIL

⁵⁷ Such as forts at the bottom of valleys, see: “Restrepo”

⁵⁸ The Iraq theatre was always going to lead to an insurgency. But the arrogance to fire the Iraqi Army was probably not the wisest move. Or was it designed to create an endless war theatre for the MIC?

CENTCOM⁵⁹ and NATO collapse, what would be the ability to repulse? If China wins WW3.0, then will the Allies be able to communicate? And so we see that the dualistic thinking, just like the old European duels, is a zero-sum game.⁶⁰

Completing and Competing With Unified Strategy

The idea that only brute force “really” works is said succinctly in the following boxer idiom, “Everyone has a plan until they get punched in the face.” Russia has a strategy, the USA has one, China, India, Pakistan have one... but what are they made of? Now, the US is moving towards a high tech, low T-signal⁶¹ military, that is “diverse” and “inclusive” (to gather more IQ and manpower). This is probably in response to similar analyses to the author’s⁶² but most likely due to a more worrying concern than not having a lot of raw male muscle in the military for infantry work: a shortage of recruits all around. What would this mean? It would mean that low educational standards, high obesity rates, and high distraction levels (entertainment and obsession with sex and drug use) and possibly high rates of anti-patriotism (due to socialist pathogen) are pervading recruitment ages. A weak crop, so to speak. That would explain the move to get girls to be part of the Selective Service. If the Pentagon has identified a manpower weakness, which would only exacerbate the IQ asset shortage, and consumption shortage (and all that entails⁶³) such as microchips, then they will have to be mitigated *by any means necessary*.

That means, already at the outset before fighting breaks out - in this very moment of the WW3.0 - that it is already in an Asymmetric environment and entering an Unorthodoxy. Conventional means will decrease, and unconventional combinations of Unorthodox, Orthodox, and Asymmetry will accelerate. Pretty soon, military boot camps will not even need to train with firearms, though they should because one day it will snap back the other direction.

It is too late to fix the world situation the way General Patton smartly identified. It was “wrong” but also would have saved the world a load of trouble later. But what is required *in the now* is direct competitiveness, and the will to win at all costs. And that simply isn’t allowed by the politically correct. It is against new [unrealistic] conventions. It is against war’s own protocols, forgetting the protocols of civil justice!

In such a situation, it is imperative that the Allies and associated countries (like Brazil, India, Mexico, etc.) learn to complete strategies through unification under the Total War doctrine⁶⁴. Or give up and let China win. A bully doesn’t give you any other choice. You either conform or do not. The CCP bully learned from the best in history, the Empire of the USA ®. Now the question is, can Americans, and the West, recall any of that former glory, former freedom-loving, high-will⁶⁵ signal?

The author cannot answer that today or tomorrow, though he has his suspicions. It will be seen in how westerners deal tactfully in their own lives, with the Changes, and with the “Changing World Order’s”⁶⁶ “Great

⁵⁹ <https://www.defense.gov/Our-Story/Combatant-Commands/>

⁶⁰ In duels, if you lose you die, if you win, you’re an outlaw. In America they solved this by having duels on county borders. Duels became, also, more and more for show of honor than victory, and this of course is not how war works in reality, even if it did for the southern gentry!

⁶¹ Read: low testosterone

⁶² https://www.academia.edu/50652106/China_vs_the_World_IQ_as_a_Strategic_Asset_a_graphical_comparison

⁶³ Weaker demand means, at the end of the day, a drop in demand as well as higher prices.

⁶⁴ <https://www.britannica.com/topic/total-war>

⁶⁵ zhi 志

⁶⁶ “The Changing World Order: Why Nations Succeed and Fail,” R. Dalio, 2021

Reset.”⁶⁷ If the populace responds to the need, then they will pass that onto the youth who will take that into the military, police, and politics, and make it happen. So far, it looks to be going the opposite. In which case it is clear which is the stronger signal.

Perhaps the Shi⁶⁸ is just stronger because hardly anyone in the west understands that the CCP has adopted a Total War by Unified Polar Strategy (TWUPS) mentality. Most have reactions such as scoffing, dismissing, guffawing, and even defending the actions of China. Not only that they “controlled the pandemic so well”⁶⁹ (nevermind that they did so through monstrosity⁷⁰) but even excusing their involvement in what was obviously an asymmetric operation. It was more common to see people turn to racist ideas about how Chinese people eat, than to recognize a well engineered plannedemic⁷¹ as what it was: a first new use of a Weapon of Mass Destruction.

MIMSical Lessons of the First American Civil War

Before we head into a second civil war, it would be nice if people familiarize themselves with second or third tier studies of the Civil War, so that they cease to have a dualistic sense of the lessons of America’s costliest and deadliest war. Maybe they would even stop hating their neighbors.

Lincoln himself was quite a paradox of unique thinking, and from the author’s home state of Kentucky. So was his enemy, Jefferson Davis, and the two shared many things in common. Quite contrarily to Robert E. Lee, Abraham Lincoln would have preserved the institution of slavery if he felt it would keep the Union.⁷² He very much believed in the power of the Federal Government and its right to dictate to the subordinate states⁷³ the economic and political gestalt of a unified government.⁷⁴ He felt it could, for example, create a central bank if it wanted to. His wife, Mary Todd Lincoln⁷⁵, saw the White House as a form of palace and spent all the budget for four years in one, to change the home into that sort of vision.⁷⁶ They were aristocratic in their demeanor, and although opposed to the lifestyle of Henry Clay⁷⁷ (deceased), admirers of his way of living and of his statesmanship. It was his ideal of compromising where possible to keep the peace.

⁶⁷ <https://www.weforum.org/focus/the-great-reset>

⁶⁸ See MIMS 2.6.1 & https://www.academia.edu/40287817/Understanding_Chess_I_The_Art_of_Chess

⁶⁹ [https://www.thelancet.com/journals/laninf/article/PIIS1473-3099\(20\)30800-8/fulltext](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/laninf/article/PIIS1473-3099(20)30800-8/fulltext)

⁷⁰ <https://www.washingtonpost.com/opinions/2020/02/06/warning-chinese-authoritarianism-is-hazardous-your-health/>

⁷¹ <https://rumble.com/ve36r3-plandemic-documentary-the-hidden-agenda-behind-covid.html>

⁷² “In August 1862, Lincoln stated: “If I could save the union without freeing any slaves I would do it; and if I could save it by freeing all the slaves I would do it; and if I could save it by freeing some and leaving others alone I would also do that.” https://www.digitalhistory.uh.edu/disp_textbook.cfm?smtID=3&psid=393

⁷³ <https://quod.lib.umich.edu/j/jala/2629860.0010.103/--abraham-lincoln-and-federalism?rgn=main;view=fulltext>

⁷⁴ <https://billofrightsinstitute.org/activities/did-abraham-lincoln-exceed-his-presidential-powers-during-the-civil-war>

⁷⁵ From the author’s home city of Lexington, KY, the “Athens of the West”

⁷⁶ <https://www.whitehouse.gov/about-the-white-house/first-families/mary-todd-lincoln/>

⁷⁷ Also of Lexington, KY. He ran for President four times and was unable to win. However, his Compromises were legendary. His cousin, Cassius Clay, for whom Muhammed Ali (of Louisville, KY) was named, was an infamous emancipationist, and fled to Russia for a time. His wife ran the White Hall estate and sold livestock to the north and the south. She was a unique woman who had indoor plumbing installed on the 2nd floor in the mid 19th century! She dumped Cassius Clay when he returned from Russia with a mistress. You can visit White Hall, and see the slave shackles in the basement from his father’s abuse of slaves. The Henry Clay estate, Ashland, by contrast, is a more sublime experience, tempered by the reality of a “nice,” but still enslaved environment. You can buy ice cream on the grounds.

By contrast the situation was not tenable,⁷⁸ and there was no way to reconcile the issue without war.⁷⁹ Therefore Lincoln used every means of verbal assault to inflame the situation and quickly.⁸⁰ He was insulting (and perhaps rightly so) to the southerner,⁸¹ his way of life,⁸² and all the evils that he had grown despondent of after he left Kentucky⁸³ to pursue a political career. His methods were to hit them high, and low, to be conventionally superior, even bulldog like and a bully, and to be tactfully superior. Superior in actions (like the Gettysburg Address⁸⁴) and in the moral standing of history.⁸⁵

It cost him his life, but he won.

What kind of lessons can we draw from the MIMS of war in the MIMS of strategy? It is that even with an excellent strategy, one may have the life drained from one by much war and conflict. The Bible taught this in many places, but it is the story of the general Wu Qi which the author most enjoys,

*“In the wake of Wu Qi's reforms, Chu's prowess was quickly manifest: Chu defeated the Yue state in the south and the Wei in the north, dealing with each in quick succession. However, King Dao died that same year. The old nobles plotted to assassinate Wu Qi at King Dao's funeral, where he would be separated from the army. Wu Qi spotted the assassins armed with bows, and rushed to the side of King Dao's body. **He was killed, but many arrows struck the dead King.** The new King Su (楚肃王), furious at his father's body being mutilated, ordered all nobles involved to be executed, along with their families.”⁸⁶*

Conclusion

Many lessons about strategy, particularly the issue of polar completeness as opposed to dualism, can be elicited from endless study of history, especially Roman and Chinese. That would take up more space than was promised. We have instead come to a place where the author feels the point is reached: a polar complete examination of the MIMS strategy will be superior to dualistic treatments.

How will they be superior? For starters, in avoiding the “sequel no one really wants.”⁸⁷ Secondly, for all intents and purposes, even if one super empire should win, or the other, and quickly, that will be superior to a

⁷⁸ https://www.nber.org/system/files/working_papers/w25197/w25197.pdf

⁷⁹ <https://www.battlefields.org/learn/articles/reasons-secession>

⁸⁰ <https://www.npr.org/2010/10/11/130489804/lincolns-evolving-thoughts-on-slavery-and-freedom>

⁸¹ <https://civilwar.vt.edu/the-debate-about-lincoln-what-did-southern-unionists-think-of-the-great-emancipator/>

⁸²

<https://www.northernpolarbears.com/site/handlers/filedownload.ashx?moduleinstanceid=1073&dataid=4447&FileName=k5e15dad.pdf>

⁸³ Ironically the state remained officially neutral in the Civil War, but Lincoln said “I must have Kentucky,” and he took her early on, and never let her go. The rebels took to marauding, which only inflamed the population or made it at least sympathetic to the Union. Reality is that the Union held Kentucky regardless, and there weren’t enough plantations to be politically feasible to defend the dying institution of slavery. Therefore his strategy was perfect. He controlled the majority of resources, waterways, and the Ohio and many other great rivers, in a very short period of time. The remainder of the war was almost theatre after that, from an Art of War perspective. For this coup, and the naval blockade, created an excellent “encirclement” of the Confederacy, and that meant eventual strangulation.

<https://thekeep.eiu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=4675&context=theses>

⁸⁴ <https://www2.ed.gov/programs/racetothetop/communities/day-1-gettysburg-address.pdf>

⁸⁵ <https://newrepublic.com/article/114029/how-lincolns-efforts-compromise-helped-end-slavery>

⁸⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wu_Qi

⁸⁷ MIMS 2.8, Ibid., pp. 49

long drawn out conflict. And yet, both are likely to collapse for different reasons.⁸⁸ Dropping the “bad boy” “supercop”⁸⁹ schtick would help America find her balance and place in the world, and to remember God. Overthrowing socialism and Communist regimes worldwide and especially in China can only come from deep internal desire of the People.

What cannot be allowed to happen is for bad strategy, worse tactics, and a fake understanding of both to allow China to rule the New World Order’s vaunted “One World Government,” under a technocracy of social credit, organ harvesting, etc.

If it takes diversity to do that, fine. If it takes more alpha males, fine. If it takes 10,000 MOABs instead of 1 well placed tactical nuke, fine. But if it can possibly take none of that, and only the will to understand the Polar Complete Whole, and to sacrifice a well chosen martyr (like Abraham Lincoln,) then all the better. But none of it will make a whole lot of sense, if the MIMS is turned into a world wide anti-MIMS all over some failed philosophy from the past. If no one explores strategy’s axioms, idioms, etc. hoping to understand how to bring about what the People need, and want, merely because of laziness, or arrogance, this is a disaster of unconscionable levels. That is what has characterized the War on Terror thus far, and this is what is so concerning about new developments in Afghanistan now.⁹⁰

The author loves to point out that dualism is demanding you pick pie *or* cake and eat only that, forever. But that isn’t so. If a MIMS fundamentally *can* be used to engineer the future in the now, then we have a responsibility to consider strategic (or anti-strategic) objectives by the context of “how did they perform in the recent past” and “how are they likely to perform in the near future” so that we can consider what will be the likely outcome.

The author, so far, does not see that as a common discourse. Nor does it even seem likely in an environment where open, truthful discourse is attacked by socialist antigens and scrutinizing antibodies alike.

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⁸⁸ China due to its GDP, America due to its penchant for following Rome into the annals of history; same thought strains, same outcomes?

⁸⁹ “To infiltrate a drug cartel, police Inspector Chan Ka Kui (Jackie Chan) goes undercover in a Chinese prison. There, he earns the trust of Panther (Yuen Wah), a cartel member, by breaking him out of prison. With the help of another undercover agent (Michelle Yeoh), they travel to Hong Kong and join up with Panther’s gang. Ka Kui is accepted by the gang’s leader (Ken Tsang), but his operation is jeopardized when Ka Kui’s girlfriend (Maggie Cheung) accidentally reveals his true identity.” “Police Story 3: Supercop,” 1992

⁹⁰ <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-49192495>

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